

Synthesis of Possible Antifertility Compounds: Part II. Synthesis of Bis-dichloroacetyl Derivatives of some Acid Hydrazides

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Several bis-(dichloroacetyl) derivatives of amino-acid hydrazides and dibasic acid hydrazides have been prepared with a view to studying their antifertility activity.

Recently it has been found that certain (bis-dichloroacetyl) diamines selectively inhibit spermatogenesis in various animals and men, interrupting the androgenic activity of the testes¹⁻³. These drugs are not, however, free from side effects. The compounds were therefore suitably modified retaining the dichloroacetamide group as a pharmacophore moiety. Considering that the dichloroacetyl hydrazides may get hydrolysed by the proteolytic enzymes present in the gonadal cells, several dichloroacetyl derivatives of the hydrazides of amino-acids and dibasic acid have been synthesised using the acid residue as biological "carriers" for the introduction of the toxic residue for cellular metabolism,⁴⁻⁷ with the hope of producing more specific agents.

The amino-acid esters and dibasic acid esters were first converted to their hydrazides which were subsequently dichloroacetylated, resulting in the formation of the following types of compounds (I-IV):

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

1. Beyler *et al.*, *Endocrinology*, 1961, 69, 819.
2. Coulston *et al.*, *Toxicol. Appl. Pharmacol.*, 1960, 2, 715.
3. Heller *et al.*, *ibid*, 1961, 3, 1.
4. Bergel, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1958, 68, 1238.
5. Ishidate *et al.*, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1955, 44, 132.
6. Nayalan and Busch, *Chem. & Eng. News*, 1958, 46,
7. Danicelli, *Nature*, 1952, 170, 863.

EXPERIMENTAL

Amino-acid esters were prepared according to the method of Kasperowski *et al.*⁸ The hydrazides were prepared by refluxing amino-acid esters (1M) and 80% hydrazine hydrate (5M) in a small amount of ethanol for 2 hr. The ethanol and the excess N_2H_4 were removed *in vacuo*.

The hydrazides of the other series were obtained by the usual methods.

NN^2 -Bis-dichloroacetyl amino-acid-hydrazides (I).—To the hydrazide (0.01M), anhydrous pyridine (10-15 ml) was added and the solution kept at 5-10° and subsequently dichloroacetyl chloride (0.025M) was added dropwise, when an exothermic reaction took place. After keeping the reaction mixture for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., it was diluted with water (25-30 ml) when a solid separated; it was shaken with HCl conc., (10-12 ml), filtered, washed with water, and recrystallised from ethanol. The m.p., yields, and analyses of the derivatives are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I
(vide Structure I)

R (Amino-acid) residue	M.P.*	% Yield	Formula	Nitrogen (%)	
				Found	Reqd.
Glycine	232°	60	$C_6H_7O_3N_3Cl_4$	13.02	13.51
α -Alanine	183°	75	$C_7H_9O_3N_3Cl_4$	12.58	12.93
α -Amino- <i>n</i> - butyric acid	120°	70	$C_8H_{11}O_3N_3Cl_4$	11.93	12.41
Valine	224°	80	$C_9H_{13}O_3N_3Cl_4$	11.62	11.90
Isoleucine	209°	55	$C_{10}H_{15}O_3N_3Cl_4$	11.18	11.45
Methionine	208°	85	$C_9H_{13}O_3N_3Cl_4S$	10.63	10.93
Phenylglycine	226°	68	$C_{12}H_{11}O_3N_3Cl_4$	10.68	10.85
β -Alanine	230°	60	$C_7H_9O_3N_3Cl_4$	12.78	12.93

*All the m.p.s. are uncorrected.

NN^2 -Bis-dichloroacetyl aminobenzoic acid hydrazides (II), N^2N^2 -bis-dichloroacetyl aliphatic (III) and N^2N^2 -bis-dichloroacetyl aromatic dibasic acid hydrazides (IV) were prepared by the following simplified procedure.

The hydrazide (0.01M), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (15-20 ml), was maintained at 5-10° and dichloroacetyl chloride (0.025M) was added dropwise with shaking when an exothermic reaction took place and immediately a white solid was obtained. It was kept for 15-20 min., filtered, washed with little HCl, (conc.), water, and recrystallised from ethanol.

The m.p., yield, and analyses of the derivatives of amino-benzoic acid hydrazides, aliphatic dibasic acid hydrazides and aromatic dibasic acid hydrazides are recorded in Table II,

TABLE II

Aminobenzoic acid hydrazides (II)

Amino-benzoic acid	M.P.	%Yield	Formula	%Nitrogen	
				Found	Reqd.
<i>Ortho</i>	224-5°	70	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₄	10.68	11.26
<i>Meta</i>	188°	70	"	10.96	11.26
<i>Para</i>	250°	68	"	10.84	11.26

Aliphatic dibasic acid hydrazides (III)

1	220-1°	55	C ₇ H ₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₄	15.72	15.82
2.	211°	60	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₄	15.0	15.22
3	220°	61	C ₉ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₄	14.52	14.66
4	242°	56	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₄	13.98	14.14

Aromatic dibasic acid hydrazides (IV)

Homophthallic	250°	40	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₄	13.17	13.46
Terephthallic	250°	45	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₄	13.0	"

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